

Introduction:

This is my experiment with elemental chemistry to make the schizophrenic element.

Discussion:

Assumption 1: The matter of schizophrenia is black fluctuation matter. Therefore black matter stones and liquid fluctuation matter will be used as the source.

Assumption 2: With the apparent quality of a split mind, therefore split language, double talk, reflective fusion synthesis will be used, therefore a split of two black matter stones in the mixture.

Assumption 3: I have to wait around an hour and a half for the mixture to synthesise.

Note 1: I use sugar as the base for the water, and dissolve the sugar into the nothingness of sweet water.

Here is the picture of the experiment:

The code of this mixture is:

1. North Nis
2. North east gc
3. East hh
4. West ti
5. South west mz
6. South ao
7. South east r0
8. North west e1
9. True north es01

Results:

While waiting for this mixture to synthesise, the mixture has started giving off a syndromal aura.

First thoughts after drinking this mixture: Yeah, Im it, im the invincible one. I wouldn't mind scooby do who who who (echo). I am experiencing paranoid calmness.

Everyones the fudge packer.

Yeah ill get my v drink, it gives me power.

I'd smash a dwarf in the back of the head.

Im a galant knight, ever so tight.

I am getting a feeling that someone is looming over me.

I feel paranoid that people are taking my power.

Saw a sheep statue in the backyard, and yeah your it, as I felt paranoid that that statue is sentient.

I feel as if my energy is based on power.

Yeah, Im basically a tank.

And end.